

ASSESSING THE SOCIOECONOMIC CONSEQUENCES OF INCREASING DIVORCE RATE IN FAISALABAD DIVISION, PAKISTAN

Samia Yousaf¹, Rakhshanda Kousar¹, Iqra Asad², Ameen Ullah^{*3}, Javaria Nasir¹

¹Institute of Agricultural and Resource Economics, Faculty of Social Science, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Pakistan

²Govt Guru Nanak Graduate College Nankana Sahib

³Department of Agriculture Economics, Balochistan Agriculture College, Quetta, Pakistan.

^{*}ameenullah.pk@yahoo.com/kakaruaf@yahoo.com

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Corresponding Author: *
Ameen Ullah

Abstract

Divorce is a major societal issue as it destabilizes the basic family unit in the society. Pakistan, like many other nations, has been experiencing alarming increase in the rates of divorce. Though divorce, in some instances, would be a relief to continued misery, it usually results in annihilation of family goals, dreams, and goals, resulting in severe emotional pain and leaving the children uncertain of their future. In most instances, divorce would lead to a decrease in the total income of the parties involved and also a greater burden on the parties. The separation of resources and legal costs is another drain on financial assets that decreases the level of economic stability. Research has indicated that women, especially those who have divorced experience more financial difficulty than men. This paper explores what is causing the rising divorce rate and evaluates the socio-economic implications of the current trend in Faisalabad Division, Pakistan. The research was carried out within Faisalabad Division in the Province of Punjab, through purposive multistage sampling method. Purposive sampling was used to select 120 respondents who were then sampled using snowball. Data collection was conducted by a well-designed pre-tested questionnaire. Two models were used in the study, a bivariate probit regression model to determine the socio-economic consequences of divorce, and a model of logistic regression to determine those factors that affect the rate of divorce. The results suggest that people in financial problems are more likely to get divorced, and media addiction also influences the divorce rate positively, but marginally. This research highlights the complexity of divorce, and the factors which effectively lead to divorce include financial stress, female economic autonomy, lack of employment by husbands, and age among other factors which might need further inquiry with more population so as to have a full understanding of what they do.

INTRODUCTION

Human beings believe that home is the best place to be in on Earth because people feel safe physically, emotionally, and spiritually in their homes. Islam sees marriage as a two-fold religious and legal institution

which enshrines a husband and wife and gives different liabilities to each one of them (Mattoo & Ashai, 2012). The rate of divorce in the modern society is on the increase due to social insecurity and

changing expectations of partners. A divorce ends marriage and abandons any rights, social or any other rights associated with such a relationship (Ahmad, 2003). In the Islamic Sharia, a husband can instigate divorce, but a woman who instigates divorce is reported to have instigated a Khula (Rahimi et al., 2012). Family and social issues often force women to strive to rescue their marriages; however, they divorce because of various causes such as economic struggle, social status deprivation, age differences, family disharmony, and many more. Although Islam protects the rights of women, in traditional societies, women have no easy access to these rights, which is often the case (Ahmed et al., 2015). Divorce is defined as a lawful but undesirable practice in the Islamic religion. The Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) said: The divorce is his most disliked among those who are allowed. It is declared in the Holy Quran: Be benevolent and just to your wives. Although he or she might not be pleased with everything it is probable that Allah has given them a bigger favor (Doi, 1990). Islamic law allows divorce in certain religious conditions and is sanctioned by the decrees of the divinity. Every country has law regulating divorce. Allah Almighty intends men and women to be companions to each other to live in harmony and peace in accordance to the commands of Allah and the teachings of his Prophet. The Holy Quran states:

“And Allah has made for you your mates of your own nature, and made for you, out of them, sons and daughters and grandchildren, and provided for your sustenance of the best” (16:72)

The satisfaction and calmness within the family is based on the ability to meet each other on the level of affection, the attentiveness to the emotional state of another person, and the sustainability of open communication, which in turn is the basis of strong family relationships (Firozjaeian et al., 2018; Sattari Sefidan Jadid et al., 2018). Another important concept is conflict management; it is a positive way to strengthen family and build a healthy relationship with people (Somohano, 2013). Nevertheless, modern families must face various issues that were caused by social changes in the world, including the changes in marriage, the growing involvement of women in the labor market, and the rise in divorce rates (Shekarbeigi et al., 2016). Some of these changes have

altered family structure to accommodate smaller families, postponed marriages, and shifted to nuclear family structures. Irrespective of these changes, the family connection provides a strong foundation on the solidification of the family unit and consequently a more successful society (Moghimi et al., 2017). Divorce is one of the greatest dangers to the family unit. It often starts small and intensifies over time, leading to emotional distance, separation and ending with a court break up (Cherlin, 2017). The media has a significant role in shaping social attitudes in relation to divorce, with movies, TV shows, and celebrity campaigns popularising and mythifying celebrity breakups, which normalises divorce and changes the attitude of the masses towards it, shifting the taboo to a matter of fact (Saleem et al., 2020). In addition, too much media usage has triggered the decline of offline emotional investment between couples, further increasing marital discord (Savitri and Ulfah, 2019). It has also been noted consistently that the divorce rates around the world have been gradually increasing. In Europe, Belgium, Portugal, Luxembourg, and the United States indicate that prevalence of divorce comes between sixty and seventy percent, but in Chile, the prevalence is significantly lower, standing at around three percent (Engel, 2014). In general, Islamic jurisdictions have a lower divorce incidence that could be partly explained by the doctrinal focus on family structure preservation in Islam (Haq et al., 2020). The rate of divorce increased significantly in the post-COVID-19 period in Pakistan; the pandemic, associated with lockdowns, increased the levels of social and economic stress factors, which further increased the frequency of domestic violence (Azhar et al., 2018). In the Punjab Province, Pakistan, the number of divorce cases grew to 18901 in 2016, as a result compared to 14243 in 2012, thus illustrating the tendency of alarming growth rates (Warren, 2023). Maladaptive coping mechanisms, such as aggression or overspending, are common in divorced people who are struggling to deal with the emotional and financial costs created by the break-up of marriages (Jalal, 2023). The economic impact of divorce is great, especially on single parent families that are highly likely to be in poverty (OECD, 2008). There are numerous policy interventions that have been enacted to reduce these fiscal difficulties including social security programmes and family

legislation regulating the allocation of assets after divorce (Chowdhury, 2019). However, the economic contribution of divorce is still a complex issue as it is hard to differentiate fiscal strains that can be directly attributed to the divorce and other confounding factors (Amato, 2000). More importantly, divorce has long-term consequences on children particularly in the areas of emotional and intellectual growth. Empirical studies have always shown that the cognitive ability and economic opportunities of children brought up in divorced families are weakened compared to those brought up in intact families (Muzaffar et al., 2018; Anderson, 2014). Such a disintegration of the family structures has a negative effect on the future and the overall well-being of children. Despite the fact that both men and women are affected by the negative consequences of divorce, women and children are usually affected unfairly. Women often face both short-term and longer-term economic financial risk and psychological, social and health traumas. Divorced families can have children who experience neglect, suffer emotionally, and experience other adverse consequences (Akpan and Ezeume, 2020). Women who had been divorced and once had the means to live comfortably tend to find it hard to fit into a lower way of living and the lack of the extended family. These complications are worsened by the stigma attached to divorced women and their children in society (Rahman et al., 2013). Single mothers put children at a high risk of economic instability and poor health outcomes, including malnutrition and lack of medical care (Bhuiya and Chowdhury, 1997). This paper aims at examining the factors that led to divorce such as income levels, employment, education, social support systems, and living conditions to shed light on the effects that affect individuals and the society at large. The results will be useful to policy makers who will be in a position to appreciate the problems associated with increasing rates of divorce and come up with specific strategies that can be used to counter them. In determining the causes that lead to divorce, the study will produce meaningful results to ensure that marital relationships are enhanced and reduce the occurrence of divorce. The bottom line is to provide greater well-being to the people and strengthen the family as the foundation of a healthy, successful society.

1.1: Objectives:

- Overview of the socio economic characteristics of respondents
- To access the consequences of divorce
- To identify factors affecting divorce rate
- To suggest policy guidelines based on study findings

Literature Review:

Different factors that vary with culturally diverse backgrounds and demographics impact divorce, and it demonstrates a complex interaction of societal, economic, and personal problems. Acharya (1998) in Nepal found that educational disparities, occupational differences, social, and familial backgrounds were the major causes of divorce. There were also factors of sexual incompatibility and the variance in economic expectations. Stevenson and Wolfers (2007) pointed out that there has been an increase in divorce rates in the past, but the rates have recently gone down as a result of delayed marriage, remarriage and changing social ideals like cohabitation. In their study, Parvin et al. (2011) in Tehran concentrated on emotional divorce, showing that the influence of financial pressures, family discipline and power were significant factors predetermining dissolution. Brown and Lin (2012) reported that in older people, the rates of divorce increased twofold between 1990 and 2010 and that remarriage and duration of marriage became notable predictors. Ghaffarzadeh and Nazari (2012) focused on adverse effects of divorce on mental health and economic welfare, and their findings showed that marital imbalances are the catalyst of dissolution. Clayton et al. (2013) investigated the media as a factor that reported that increased media consumption had a negative relationship outcome particularly in short-term relationships. Zafar and Kausar (2014) demonstrated that divorced women had high rates of stress, anxiety, and loneliness and indicated the role of social support in reducing the impacts. The economic repercussions of divorce have been found to differ between genders (Brockel and Andreb 2015) with women tending to experience more negative impact, even though they are more likely to engage in the labour-force market. According to Hoseini and Rezapour, (2015), such significant causes of divorce included familial interference, addiction and unmet

expectations, whereas Mahmood et al. (2016) cited increasing divorce rates in Pakistan due to early marriages and socio-economic strains. Sari et al. (2016) found that low-context communication and low socio-economic status were good predictors of risk of divorce. Lastly, Wazeema and Jayathunga (2017) examined the issue of divorce in the Muslim community in Sri Lanka, and they discovered that any adverse effects of divorce surpassed any favorable outcomes. All these works highlight the complexity of divorce, in which socio-cultural and economic as well as individual factors are essential in the formation of marital stability. Ramzan et al. (2018) stated that such driving factors include financial stress, joblessness, lack of trust, and the achievement gap in education, whereby a disturbing pattern of rising divorce rates is observed and may lead to lack of stability in family arrangements. Damota (2019) has studied the drastic societal and personal effects of divorce, documenting the outcomes, including school dropout, delinquency, and custody problems in children, which is why intervention methods were necessary to improve the situation. According to findings of Khan et al. (2019), economic difficulties, domestic violence, and sexual incompatibility were the main reasons of divorce in Pakistan, where financial and emotional repercussions were overwhelmingly insurmountable among children. Fahad and Khan (2020) identified economic pressures and high educational costs, especially women empowerment as a key element in marriage stresses and the reduction of the Parda as a source of marriage dissatisfaction. With the law allowing women to divorce, Patoari (2020) noted that in Bangladesh, divorce has significant economic and emotional impacts on the former; hence, stigma development in society. According to Pothan (2020), in the Hindu society, domestic violence, adultery, and in-law interference were the leading factors that cause divorce, and the psychological effects of the act include loneliness and inferiority complex that both genders experience after divorce. According to Sheykhi (2020), modernization and higher education rates led to the increased divorce rates, particularly in developing countries, where women experience acute social and economic hardships after the divorce. Waseem et al. (2020) specifically addressed the issue of psychosocial problems of divorced women in Pakistan and emphasized the importance of societal

norms that aggravate the emotional state and the need to make changes. Other studies in various areas also highlighted the contribution of economic stress and its effect on divorce rates. Abdulrahman and Alamri (2021) in Saudi Arabia found that personality differences, unequal allocation of labour, and spousal lack of attention were some of the leading factors in divorce, and the policy reforms are necessary to reduce them. In the study, Amri et al. (2022) analyzed the relationship between poverty and divorce in Indonesia, and the results showed that the impact of poverty on divorce rates can be alleviated by the financial independence of women. In Pakistan, Rubab and Alam (2022) established that infertility, family violence, and media addiction were often major factors contributing to divorce and therefore, interventions were essential to deal with these influences on the society. All these studies show that divorce is a complex issue that requires a multifaceted approach where the economic, psychological, and cultural aspects are taken into consideration in order to reduce its adverse effects on people and communities

Materials and Methods

The current research was conducted in Faisalabad, the third-largest urban centre in Pakistan, due to its highly diverse population, fast urbanisation process, economic eminence, the concentration of educational institutions, well-developed healthcare system, and the high level of cultural diversity. These features make the city an ideal place to study the dynamics of divorce and the socio-economic consequences of divorce. The purposive sampling was first used in order to find participants who were the most open to the research goals, and snowball sampling was used then to guarantee the sufficient number of respondents. One hundred and twenty women who were divorced were chosen, which can be attributed to the strict selection criteria taken in line with Etikan and colleagues (2016). The semi-structured interviews, carried out with the help of a detailed questionnaire, were used to extract data. The questionnaire was originally written in English and later translated into the native languages of the participants and consisted of four parts. Invitations were sent to 150 people, out of which 135 people sent back filled survey, 120 out of them participated in full interview. The fieldwork

was spread over a few districts: 20 participants were interviewed in Jaranwala, 40 in Jumrah and 30 in other parts of Faisalabad, 15 respondents in Smundri responded to the email and five respondents in Tandlianwala were interviewed via telephone. The length of interviews was twenty to forty minutes. After data was collected, it was vetted, assigned serial numbers, and inputted into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet so that it can be completed and further statistical analysis can be conducted.

Econometric Model

Bivariate Probit Regression model was applied to analyse the interdependence of two dichotomous dependent variables. This model was chosen because it was able to estimate various outcomes at once and also take into consideration the possible correlations of the dependent variables. The dichotomous character of these effects a financial burden and a mental health problem makes the Bivariate Probit very suitable to describe interdependence and address endogeneity and serial correlation issues. The overall structure of the model is:

$$Y_1^* = \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_k X_k + \varepsilon_1$$

$$Y_2^* = \alpha_1 X_1 + \alpha_2 X_2 + \dots + \alpha_k X_k + \varepsilon_2$$

Here, Y_1^* and Y_2^* are latent variables representing the unobserved propensity for experiencing financial challenges and mental health issues, respectively. Y_1 and Y_2 are the observed binary outcomes. X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k are independent variables, and $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_k$ and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_k$ are coefficients to be estimated. The error terms ε_1 and ε_2 are assumed to follow a standard bivariate normal distribution with zero means, unit variances, and correlation coefficient ρ .

Variables Used in the Model

Dependent Variables:

- Financial Problems: Signs of economic or financial hardship, impoverishment or indebtedness after divorce.
- Mental Health Status: Psychological well-being and mental functioning during the post-divorce period.

Independent Variables

- Age: The effect of age on financial issues mediated by career stage and income potential.
- Education: It is assumed that a greater level of education will increase its chances of employment and resultant financial stability.
- Number of children: As many children as possible will increase financial strain.
- Access to Healthcare Services Before Divorce:
 - Pre-divorce health care access is postulated to have an indirect, negative impact on the burden of money.
 - Healthcare Services After Divorce: Post-divorce quality of health-care can help to reduce financial pressures.
- Divorce Rate: The rate of divorce among the people affects the individual financial performance.
- Childcare Facilities: Availability of childcare services moderates the amount of resources that working parents have to use economically.

Logistic Regression Model

To measure the socio-economic predictors which affect the incidence of divorce, the logistic regression methodology is used, to model the likelihood of divorce based on the different covariates. The logistic regression equation is as follows:

$$\text{logit}(P(Y=1)) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

In this equation, $P(Y=1)$ represents the probability of divorce occurring, $\text{logit}(P(Y=1))$ is the log-odds of divorce, β_0 is the intercept term, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_n$ are the coefficients of the independent variables, and X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n are the independent variables.

Variables Used in the Model

Dependent Variable:

- Divorce Status: A binary variable that shows divorce (1) and non-divorce (0).

Independent Variables:

- Age: This is a continuous variable that shows the age of the respondents.

- Education: This is a categorical variable that signifies the education attainment.
- Number of children: Count variable that represents the size of a family.
- Financial Stress: The level of financial hardship.
- Domestic Violence: A variable that indicates that there is domestic violence.
- Media Addiction: A measurement of media consumption dependency.
- Cultural and Religious Contradictions: A binary variable which points to contradictions between cultural and religious beliefs.
- Women Independence: A scale that considers female independence dimensions.

Results and Discussion

The data are analyzed in the below section to provide a review of the core attributes and trends that the sample contains. The descriptive analysis is used to outline and highlight the findings that are relevant to the factors determining the divorce rates and the socio-economic consequences of the growing rates of divorce. Findings on each of the subgroups are outlined separately.

marriage duration, Source of income, Women income, Social status and Number of children)

The study analysed the socioeconomic characteristics influencing divorce rates and their subsequent consequences in Faisalabad. A sample of 120 divorced women was analyzed, showing diverse demographic and economic profiles. Respondents' ages vary from 19 to 45 years, with a mean of 27.17 years (SD = 5.507), indicating some relatively young ones. Educational level varied, averaging 10.32 years (SD = 5.245), suggesting a broad spectrum of educational backgrounds. Husband's income levels were highly variable, spanning from 0 to 400,000 PKR, with a mean of 58,782.61 PKR (SD = 371,659.644), highlighting significant income differences. The average duration of previous marriages was 4.41 years (SD = 4.257), reflecting different marital experiences. Ex-husbands' occupational statuses averaged 0.71 (SD = 0.715) on a scale of 0 to 2, indicating moderate occupational levels. Women's personal incomes ranged from 0 to 60,000 PKR, with a mean of 19,575 PKR (SD = 16,060.24), pointing to diverse financial independence. Social status scores averaged 0.77 (SD = 0.716) on a 0 to 2 scale, denoting moderate social standing. The average number of children per respondent was 1.80 (SD = 1.570), indicating varied family sizes.

Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Respondent (Age, Education, Husband income, Previous

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of the socio economic characteristics of the respondent

Socio economic characteristics	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std.Deviation
Age	19	45	27.17	5.507
Education	0	18	10.32	5.245
Husband income	0	100000	24210.53	26183.651
Monthly expenditure before divorce	12000	90000	34582.61	15040.870
Women income	0	60000	19575.00	16060.240
Number of children	0	9	1.80	1.570
Social status	0	2	.77	.716
Previous marriage	1	25	4.41	4.257
Valid N (line wise)				

4.6 Results of Bivariate Probit Model

Financial challenges	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Age	-.072	.027	-2.72	.007	-.125	-.02	***
Education	-.027	.032	-0.84	.4	-.09	.036	
Number of children	.222	.11	2.02	.043	.007	.438	**
Healthcare service before	-.091	.413	-0.22	.826	-.901	.719	
Healthcare services after	.499	.367	1.36	.174	-.221	1.219	
Divorce rate	1.188	.369	3.22	.001	.464	1.911	***
Childcare facilities	.102	.454	0.23	.822	-.787	.992	
Constant	1.715	.84	2.04	.041	.068	3.361	**
Mental Health status							
Age	.02	.023	0.89	.372	-.024	.065	
Education	-.005	.024	-0.19	.851	-.053	.043	
Number children	.03	.086	0.35	.723	-.138	.199	
Healthcare services before	.327	.3	1.09	.276	-.261	.915	
Healthcare sevicees after	-.42	.264	-1.59	.112	-.936	.097	**
Divorce rate	-.112	.341	-0.33	.744	-.781	.558	
Childcare facilities	.367	.329	1.12	.265	-.278	1.011	
Constant	-.453	.722	-0.63	.53	-1.868	.962	
Constant	.03	.189	0.16	.873	-.34	.4	
Mean dependent var	0.483		SD dependent var			0.502	
Number of obs	120		Chi-square			24.984	
Prob > chi2	0.035		Akaike crit. (AIC)			283.609	
*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1							

Bivariate probit regression analysis examined the socioeconomic consequences of divorce. Age negatively influenced financial challenges post-divorce (Coef. = -0.072, p = 0.007) explaining older individuals experience least financial hardships, possibly due to greater financial stability. On the other hand each additional child increased financial

challenges (Coef. = 0.222, p = 0.043), likely due to greater living expenses. Experiencing divorce itself heightened financial difficulties (Coef. = 1.188, p = 0.001), underscoring the financial strain of marital dissolution. Access to post-divorce healthcare services negatively impacted mental health status (Coef. = -0.42, p = 0.112), indicating that healthcare access may

reduce some mental health issues associated with divorce. Variables such as education level, number of

children, pre-divorce healthcare access, and childcare facilities was not significantly affect financial or mental health outcomes.

Results of Logistic Regression Model

Divorce status	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Age	.352	.138	2.55	.011	.081	.623	**
Education	.131	.075	1.75	.081	-.016	.278	*
Number of Children	-.127	.314	-0.40	.686	-.744	.489	
Financial Stress	2.066	.894	2.310	.233	.081	.623	**
Domestic violence	-.17	1.037	-0.16	.87	-2.202	1.862	
Media addiction	1.46	.81	1.802	.657	-1.948	1.228	*
Cultural religious	.213	.83	0.26	.797	-1.413	1.84	
Women independence	.341	.84	0.41	.684	-1.305	1.988	
Constant	-6.651	3.436	-1.94	.053	-13.385	.084	*
Mean dependent var		0.917		SD dependent var		0.278	
Pseudo r-squared		0.218		Number of obs		120	
Chi-square		15.004		Prob > chi2		0.059	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		71.837		Bayesian crit. (BIC)		96.924	
*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1							

Source: Author’s calculation

Logistic regression analysis highlighted factors influencing divorce rates. Age positively correlated with divorce likelihood (Coef. = 0.352, p = 0.011), implying older individuals are more vulnerable to divorce. Education level also depicts a positive trend (Coef. = 0.131, p = 0.081), suggesting higher education may be linked increase in divorce rates. Financial stress significantly increased divorce probability (Coef. = 2.066, p = 0.023), highlighting economic stress as a vital factor. Media addiction was marginally associated with higher divorce rates (Coef. = 1.46, p = 0.081), indicating that excessive media consumption might contribute to marital uncertainty. However, factors like number of children, domestic violence, cultural or religious beliefs, and women's independence was not show significant effects on divorce rates.

These findings suggest that age, education, financial stress, and media addiction are significant factors determining divorce rates and their socioeconomic consequences in Faisalabad. Older age and higher education levels are connecting to higher divorce rates, while financial stress shows financial challenges post-divorce. Media addiction may also play a role in marital instability. To address these matter, it is recommended to strengthen financial support systems for divorced individuals, enhance access to mental health services, promote financial literacy, address media consumption habits, build robust social support networks, reform family laws, and invest in relationship education. These interventions aim to mitigate the adverse effects of divorce and support affected individuals in Faisalabad.

Conclusion

This current study examined the socioeconomic factors and consequences of divorce in a group of 120 women living in Faisalabad. As the empirical data showed, most of the respondents were rather young; the mean age was about 27 years, and the average level of education background was about ten years of schooling. The sharp income disparity between married couples appeared and the importance of financial reliance of women and their increased vulnerability after divorce were highlighted. The average marital life was more than four years and majority of the participants had almost two children, further enhancing the weight of family commitments after the marital separation. Regression through a bivariate probit model showed that older women had more financial misfortunes, as compared to the many children who increased fiscal problems. The process of divorce itself significantly increased economic stress; the use of healthcare services after divorce, in turn, reduced the psychological stress. Age, educational level, financial strain, and media dependence were found as the salient predictors of divorce through logistic regression modelling with financial strain showing the greatest impact. Interestingly, cultural norms, domestic violence, as well as autonomy of women, did not demonstrate as statistically significant determinants. Together, the research concludes that divorce in Faisalabad is not only an individual or family dilemma but a much more general socioeconomic issue influenced by financial constraints, educational levels and social behavior. To overcome these issues, it is recommended to increase financial aid provisions, expand access to mental health services, develop financial literacy, change marriage law, and develop relationship education. Such interventions can be used to reduce the rate of divorce, offer support to the women who have been affected and enhance community resilience and social stability.

Recommendations

- **Strengthen Financial Support Systems:** Develop targeted financial assistance for divorced individuals, particularly those with children.
- **Enhance Access to Mental Health Services:** Improve mental health care and

support networks to help divorced individuals cope with emotional challenges.

- **Promote Financial Literacy and Education:** Implement programs to improve financial management and job skills among divorced individuals.
- **Address Media Consumption Habits:** Promote healthier media consumption through public campaigns and educational initiatives.
- **Strengthen Support Networks:** Build community support through counseling and social networks for divorced individuals.
- **Reform Family Law:** Ensure fair and transparent divorce proceedings and asset distribution.
- **Invest in Relationship Education:** Provide education on communication and conflict resolution to reduce divorce rates.

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